

Code of Conduct

Established in 1997, the Nexus Research Group (NRG) is New Zealand's only school based research organisation.

Purpose: To foster a lively curiosity about the world we live in by providing challenging and stimulating learning experiences through real on-going scientific investigations. The emphasis will be on developing problem solving skills, technical skills, analytical skills, and communication skills. Involvement in this group should not impinge on the students normal classroom work (including homework or assignments).

Value: Working in the NRG would provide an insight for students interested in attending university or provide work experience for the job market. Opportunities may arise to explore issues surrounding ethics and being a responsible citizen.

Supervision: The scientist in charge and Director of the NRG, Michael Fenton, has had many years industrial, teaching and research experience. He was a Ministry of Education e-Learning Fellow and received a Microsoft Innovative Teacher award. Students also have access to a network of advisers from research and government agencies both nationally and overseas.

As a member of the Nexus Research Group students will be expected to exhibit the following traits:

- **Trustworthiness** - you will only use materials or equipment that you are permitted to.
- **Honesty** - you will record all results without bias.
- you will acknowledge sources of information and significant contributions from others.
- **Safety** - you will make yourself aware of and follow all safety precautions including any Safety and Health regulations and any other laws or regulations relating to your project.
- you will not put others at risk by any action or failure to act.
- **Cooperation** - you will be willing to share materials, equipment and information with others in the group if asked to do so.

Each student must keep appropriate records of their work. This may include

1. Materials used, including brand names and quantities
2. Methods or preparation of materials or fabrication/construction plans.
3. Raw data in the form of result tables
4. Conclusions or discussions
5. Articles **properly** referenced (including book or journal title and volume, publisher and date published, author, article title, page numbers).
6. Printouts or copies of computer source code with appropriate explanations.

- All contact with any commercial, research or other outside agencies, or individuals, including requests for equipment and funding, will be through the Director. Letters must be sent on official letterhead.
- All Nexus Research Group (NRG) projects remain the intellectual property of the Directors. Any commercial development or sharing of information that involves any part of a Nexus project will be at the discretion of and advantage to the Directors.
- You will not bring the NRG into disrepute by any actions or a failure to act in an appropriate manner.
- Failure to comply with this code of conduct may lead to dismissal from the NRG.
- The Directors and associate organisations and individuals shall not be liable for any losses or damages or any other claim made against them as a consequence of any action or inaction related to the NRG.

We understand and agree to abide by the requirements and limitations as stated above. **Date:**

Caregiver name _____

Caregiver signature _____

Student name _____

Student signature _____

Job Descriptions:

Technicians

1. Developing and trialing practical experiments or demonstrations for use in Science Fair or classroom teaching.
2. Construction or maintenance, eg, wearable art, BMX trial gate, EnviroPower circuits, assisting other researchers with practical work.
3. Help organise inter-school technology design competitions (eg, robot wars).
4. Must have or want to develop good practical skills. Someone who enjoys making things. This person does not have to be 'academic'.

Programmers

1. Developing and trialing software for Mac OSX or WINDOWS.
2. Create games and simulations for use in teaching.
3. Help organise inter-school game design competitions.
4. Must have or want to develop good programming skills. Someone able to work as part of a team. Programme source code to stay with the NRG.

Researchers/Specialists

1. Research and analyse literature (eg, global warming, smart alloys in clothing).
2. Evaluate information for seminars and reports (to others in the group initially).
3. Pursue longer term projects to completion, perhaps oversee particular projects as a manager.
4. Must have or want to develop good analytical and communication skills. Someone able to work with minimal supervision. Someone willing to pass on their knowledge and skills to others.

Special Interest Groups (SIG's)

Students may wish to collaborate as part of a focus group or special interest group. Examples from past years included the following SIG's:

- Communications
- Information Systems
- Space Exploration
- Microbiology

Can you meet the challenge?

Safety, honesty, trustworthiness and co-operation are expected to the highest standard.

Any unacceptable behaviour or conduct will result in immediate expulsion from the group.

Only serious students will be able to fulfil the job descriptions.

QUESTION EVERYTHING